

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

EVACUATION AND ACTIVITIES OF THE STALINGRAD MILITARY AVIATION SCHOOL IN THE CITY OF KUSTANAI

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Abstract

The article discusses the process of evacuation of the Stalingrad military aviation school to the city of Kustanai, accommodation, organization of the training process for cadets. Military equipment was transported under its own power, there were interruptions with food. With the evacuation of the military state farm from the village of Rossoshka, the issue of food was partially resolved. Entire blocks were allocated for teachers and cadets in the city of Kustanai. As the cadets saw the city of Kustanai, many saw camels for the first time. During the period of evacuation in Kustanai, the school prepared a large number of pilots for the front, who became famous pilots who accomplished feats during the war. Some became cosmonauts in the future and in peacetime gave a lot to the country.

Keywords: Stalingrad military aviation school, evacuation, pilots, city of Kustanai.

Introduction. The need to provide specialised military personnel was a paramount task for the USSR and the Communist Party. With the change in military technologies and technical means, new military specialists were required for a change in the tactics and strategy of military combat, and they were also supposed to receive education in military educational institutions. As previously thought, it is no longer relevant or criminal in relation to the state. The USSR was in a difficult geopolitical situation, surrounded by not always friendly states, so the militarization of almost all spheres of society was a reasonable strategy at that time. The image of the enemy did not apply to a specific country but was more of a collective nature, but the citizens of the country were prepared according to the principle that "if there is war tomorrow", everyone should be ready. Therefore, the norms "ready for work and defence" (hereinafter TRP) developed so actively that they were aimed at the physical strengthening of the health and development of the Soviet citizen. But one thing is not a hindrance to the other, young people learned to jump with a parachute, army-crawling, throw grenades, provide medical assistance, own a weapon, shoot from it, and more.

Circles of radio operators, signalmen, paratroopers, and snipers appeared; of course, passing the norms and receiving the «Voroshilov shooter» badge became mandatory for a certain age group; everything and much more involved the preparation of Soviet people for military affairs. But one of the leading military units began to take shape: tankers and pilots. The image of a tankman and a pilot was popularised in feature films ("Hearts of Four", "Pilots", "Fighters", "Heavenly Slow-moving Vehicle") and in the works of Soviet writers. The creation and later reorganisation of various socio-political organisations, for example, the Society for the Promotion of Defence, Aviation, and Chemical Construction (hereinafter referred to as Osoaviakhim), contributed to the active militarization of the population and their readiness for war.

Therefore, the opening of military educational institutions was not accidental but important. The issue of creating a flight educational institution was constantly under control, was discussed, and "in the spring of 1928, at the Plenum of the Revolutionary Military Council of the USSR, it was decided to find a place for deployment, and on February 6, 1929, an order was issued to open the Stalingrad Military Aviation School No. Stalingrad Red Banner Proletariat, to determine the location of Stalingrad" [1,p.1-5]. It was difficult and honourable to enrol in a military aviation school; for the first time, only young people were admitted from factories according to party and Komsomol recruitment. The Stalingrad aviation school was one of the best in the country. It was she who had the honour of mastering new technology with the cadets. "On May 25, 1938, the military aviation school was transformed into an aviation school" [2,p.1-5]. Both boys and girls dreamed of being pilots. The legendary flights of Valery Chkalov, the development of airspace by women Zinaida Korolina, Polina Osipenko For a long time, her hairstyle was in vogue among girls, and girls who came to hairdressers for a haircut were asked to cut it "like Polina Osipenko". The training of cadets went on as usual, but the threat of war forced them to return to the status of a military aviation school with a one-year training period already in March 1941. With the outbreak of war, the school offered cadets an accelerated training programme. The main part of the graduates went to the front, having the skills of piloting the I-16 aircraft, and only a small part - the Yak-1, which were then very few. Before the start of World War II, the aviation school was commanded by Major General A.N. Sokolov, the chief of staff was Colonel I.N. Lyshenko, the commissar brigade commissar was I.K. Workers; and the assistant head of the school for flight training was Captain P.M. Afanasyev, who later became, already in the rank of lieutenant colonel, the head of the school [3,p.1-5].

Methodology. To reveal the indicated problem of the study, the author used various sources. Published archival materials, memoirs of participants in the Great

Patriotic War, cadets of the school, museum materials. This issue got the opportunity to be studied due to the publication by archivists, museum workers of archival documents, which gave access to their study. The general theoretical and methodological base was the civilizational-formational approach in revealing both the historical background and the specific description of the activities of the military aviation school, its activities at a new location. The article is based on the principles of historicism, objectivity and citizenship, using general scientific methods of analysis, dialectical categories of causality, possibility, reality. The most important moment of the theory of knowledge is used - this is practice as the basis of knowledge and the criterion of truth; to recreate the panorama of the activity of the object under study, the use of the logic of narration, particular methods of statistics, sociology in the form of content analysis of documents, interviewing participants in the events described, a survey, archiving and hermeneutics with a comparative historical method of verification and use of sources helped to recreate the panorama of the activity of the object under study. Taking into account the subject specifics and characteristics of the tasks set, the methodological basis of this study is the principles of system analysis, specifically - historical, institutional, structural-functional and comparative approaches to considering the role of the military aviation school in the training of military personnel in the Great Patriotic War and the preparation of a professional base for the post-war period.

Results. Kazakhstan has become a place for the transfer of many strategically important objects. The Stalingrad Military Aviation School of Pilots was evacuated to the city of Kustanai. Local historians note that there were two attempts to transfer the school at the end of 1941, when the Nazis approached Moscow. On December 20, 1941, the Kustanai Regional Executive Committee of Workers' Deputies and the Bureau of the Regional Committee of the Communist Party of Kazakhstan adopted a joint resolution on the allocation of more than 30 premises, five three-tonne vehicles, and 180 specialists in construction professions. The Stalingrad school began evacuation only in June 1942; 3594 personnel, 220 aircraft, and 77 waggons were supposed to arrive. The order of the Deputy People's Commissariat of Defence for Aviation, Lieutenant General Novikov A.A., was carried out immediately. The planes got under their own power, rose in alarm, and headed north, along the Volga. They landed on the left bank of the river, where the Kachinskaya aviation school was based. At the base, the equipment was being prepared for the final flight. In total, 214 vehicles of various types departed from Stalingrad, although there are discrepancies in the numbers in some reports. 212 units flew to the city of Kustanai; one had an accident, the other had a breakdown. The personnel went on a barge along the Volga, then in a waggon by rail. The equipment consisted of UTI training aircraft and, in addition to them, 42 Yak-1 and Yak-7 fighters and 20 donkeys. For the I-16, airfields were equipped in the villages of Ozerny and Fedorovka. A runway was built for faster "yaks" on the territory of today's airport of the

city of Kustanai * (founded in 1879 as Novo-Nikolaevsk, due to the confusion of sending mail since the city with that name existed in other provinces, renamed from 1893 to 1895 as Nikolaevsk, from February 1895 to June 17, 1997 as Kustanay, then Kostanay). By July 1942, a total of 4 aviation squadrons had arrived, and by August 18, 8 echelons with personnel and property had arrived. The city of Kustanai had a wide free space for airfields, flat terrain, and often clear weather. Planned training began on September 1, 1942. The conditions of the war demanded that the aviation school train a larger number of pilots, so it reached 9–10 issues per year, 800–900 fighter pilots each, while training focused on practice. Each lead instructor accounted for up to 100 or more trained fighter pilots. Major Pavel Mikhailovich Afanasiev, assistant head of the flight training school, constantly asked to go to the front, but in the rear he did a lot of work, preparing experienced military personnel.

The divisions of the school were located in dugout towns in the vicinity of Kustanai. Aircraft workshop No. 278, which arrived from the Voronezh region with 367 workers and employees, was located in the Dzharkulskaya machine and tractor station (hereinafter referred to as MTS) [4]. The headquarters, flight training department, reserve battalion, and other services were located in the city. Entire blocks in the centre of Kustanay were allocated for the aviation school. Some of those buildings, in one form or another, have survived to this day. In the city, buildings were allocated for her from the street. Lenin (Al-Farabi) to the street. Pavlova, including St. Kalinin (Altynsarin), St. Tolstoy, Insurgent, Gogol, and the school "40 Years of October" in Narimanovka. For the garrison, the aviation school provided the building on the street. Gogol, 59. Avimasters were located in Kustanai and Fedorovsky districts—Fedorovsky grain state farm and Dzharkulskaya MTS. There was not enough production space, and in January 1943 the city leadership transferred 434.1 square metres to the aviation school at the repair plant, as well as the premises of two unfinished and mothballed workshops with an area of 88.4 square metres, which the school had to complete on its own.

From the memoirs of one of the pilot cadets, Ivan Rudenko: "At first, training flights were carried out from a civilian airfield, which was behind the railway station, but this airport was needed to transport mail and other strategic needs, so the cadets flew from airfields in the villages of Ozernoe and Fedorovka, and also additionally allocated a place in the village of Zatobolsk, as they provided additional aircraft of the I-16 class "[5, p.3-5]. From February 1 to April 25, 1943, the areas located close to the city of Kustanai were sent to clear snow from taxiways, aircraft parking, access roads, and airstrips with 20–40 workers, from 5 to 15 carts with carters, and two or three tractor drivers. The aircraft-motor park was located in the field instead of hangars or other covered facilities. In frost, rain, and wind, technical personnel had to carry out repairs and technical preparation of aircraft in a few hours instead of the norm of 2-3 days. The engineering and technical staff worked with full effort.

Another historical fact deserves attention: in 1953, in the village of Fedorovka, Fedorovsky district, German Titov also arrived as part of a squadron of pilot cadets (his letter is kept in the museum of the district) [6, p.20] A., the second person who flew into space, a pilot-cosmonaut of the USSR]. As German Titov's desire to become a pilot arose, he recalls that "once a teacher's husband came to their village with golden buttons, shoulder straps, ties, and shiny shoes, and I asked, Where do they give all this? He replied that he was in aviation" [7, p.1-25].

This is partly why, when, in 1953, a graduate of the Titov school was drafted into the army, he asked at the military registration and enlistment office to send him to serve in aviation. Titov G. studied in Kustanai, and after graduating from college, he continued his education in Novosibirsk.

Some of the cadets were accommodated in the barracks, where the house-passage of the Yaushev merchants used to be (then the building was used as a store, then after the repair the regional museum of local history is located, which itself is the history of the region), part of the flight crew was placed in private apartments, rented a corner, and food was dealt with gradually. At first, and this is understandable, the cadets did not eat and fainted during flights. Sometimes it came that "the cadets themselves were looking for food, tried to exchange for something, buy milk and shaneshki for 15 kopecks, and that's what they are fed with" [8, p.3-5]. To solve food issues, an evacuated military state farm from the village of Rossoshka was attached, with cows and land where rye and barley were sown. They were used to feed livestock, and part of them was used to feed teachers and cadets. The state farm is located south of the city along the Tobol River, in the village of Udar'nik (at present, the territorial settlement is part of the regional centre of the city of Kostanay and is one of the microdistricts). In winter, wolves often hunted, volunteers had to shoot, and the trophy was replenished with at least five or six individuals.

"For many guys who arrived in the city of Kustanai in August 1942, a picture of a provincial city appeared before their eyes, "one street was paved with cobblestones; in windy summer weather, it was covered with sand; and it stretched from the current thermal power plant (thermal power plant) to the shoe factory building (from evacuated objects) on the banks of the Tobol and bore the name of Lenin (now Al-Farabi Avenue), notes Ivan Rudenko in his memoirs; "such an appearance was characteristic of many towns, especially in difficult wartime" [9, p.60 -63].

"The city was small in its area; it occupied the territory from modern Narimanov Street (Narimanovskaya, a Tatar settlement, was located there and named after one of the famous people) to the Green Market along Pobedy Street, between plant No. 507 (514), where they produced gunpowder; it was located next to the thermal power plant and the railway station—a wasteland. With the advent of new cadets, accommodation was in the Central grocery store; at present, the Main Post Office (Kazpost) has been built in its place along Altynsarin Street. One of the cadets first saw camels here, on which they brought food from Turgay for sale at the bazaar [10, p. 3].

Conclusion. During the deployment in Kustanai from 1942 to 1946, the school trained 2444 fighter pilots for the front. In other matters, in 1946, the school decided not to return to the destroyed Stalingrad but sent it to the West Siberian District, where it worked until it was disbanded in 1961.

Among the graduates, there are about 100 heroes of the Soviet Union, and five pilots were awarded twice. The school gave a ticket to life twice: to the Hero of the Soviet Union, Air Marshal Evgeny Savitsky, Commander-in-Chief of the Air Force, and to the Hero of the Soviet Union, Air Marshal Pavel Kutakhov. During the post-war years, future pilot-cosmonauts German Titov and Boris Volynov were trained. But 21 cadets and an instructor pilot, who died during training flights, remained lying in Kustanai land. A monument was erected to them in Victory Park.

As long as we remember, the immortal regiment passes annually on Victory Day, and everyone who carries a portrait of his loved one gives them the opportunity to pass on Victory Day along the main square, then the Soviet Union's Red Square.

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